
96. Is the Earth flat?

IS THE EARTH round, or is it flat? It is a fascinating question. Asking it shows the power of enquiring minds to probe the accepted wisdom. Answering it has opened up a huge range of insights into the natural world.

AS A *scientific* question, the solution to which must fit consistently within a vast range of natural phenomena, it was answered more than two millennia ago, by the Greeks of the Hellenistic period, some 300 BCE.

Aristotle drew on arguments such as southern constellations rising higher above the horizon the further south one travels, while the shadow of the Earth on the Moon during a lunar eclipse is circular. Cleomedes, and later Eratosthenes, determined Earth's circumference by measuring the length of the Sun's shadow at one location in Egypt (Alexandria) at noon on the summer solstice when the Sun was directly overhead at Syene.

Amongst various methods for determining the Sun's distance, estimates based on the Transit of Venus gave successive improvements in the 1600s, 1700s, and 1800s.

'Direct' demonstration of Earth's spherical form followed from Ferdinand Magellan's circumnavigation of the globe between 1519–1522, while the Transglobe Expedition of 1979–1982 was the first to make a surface circumnavigation via the poles.

ANY REMAINING scientific doubt was firmly excluded by the advent of Copernicanism in the mid-1500s. This placed the Sun at the centre of the solar system, with the Earth and other planets in orbit around it. Newton's laws of gravity gave both a mathematical foundation to this hypothesis, as well as enormous predictive power which has been verified countless times since.

In practice, the Copernican 'revolution' took some decades to gain full acceptance, accompanied by a reluctance to accept the idea that the Earth is really moving through space. But from that time, until at least the mid-19th century, the idea that the Earth was 'round' rather than flat was largely unquestioned.

Since then, the scientific method of iterating observation, hypothesis, verification and prediction, has enabled scientific advances at an enormous pace.

THE SCIENTIFIC METHOD has led to innumerable advances across physics, chemistry, geology, biology, medicine, and beyond. In theoretical terms it has led to a detailed, deeply interconnected understanding of fields such as electromagnetism, optics, relativity, quantum mechanics and particle physics.

In practical terms this has, in turn, given us railways, cars, planes, televisions, mobile phones, the internet, satellite navigation, MRI... and so on. These practical advances are embraced by the vast majority, even if their roots are not necessarily well understood.

Let me continue to use the term 'round' although we now know that the Earth, largely because of its rotation, is a slightly flattened 'ellipsoid'. We can explain its form, and its structure, as arising from the complex process of planetary formation, all shaped by the force of gravity.

Along with these ideas come a vast range of experimental results, and a truly remarkable self-consistent picture, of the Earth's formation, its structure and its geological history, embracing seismology, radioactivity, plate tectonics and a host of other phenomena.

AHUGE RANGE of natural phenomena is explained by today's framework of physics and mathematics: we can comprehend and predict seasons on Earth, along with the 'wobbling' effects of precession and nutation. We can explain the motions of the planets, of planetary moons, and of other solar system bodies. We can predict eclipses, planetary transits, stellar occultations, and the path of artificial satellites like the Space Station across the night sky. It gives us Earth observation and meteorological satellites, and a multitude of geostationary, telecommunications, and global navigation satellites.

And a whole host of even more 'subtle' natural phenomena are explained (and predicted) by our current understanding of physics: amongst them, stellar and Galactic aberration, relativistic precession of the orbit of Mercury, and lunar libration, small changes in perspective and rotation which bring slightly different regions of the Moon's surface into view at different times.

The list of successes is indeed impressive. And our modern high-tech society rests firmly upon them.

WHY, THEN, DO SOME people, in the face of such towering and overwhelming evidence to the contrary, and in the absence of any other self-consistent theory, cling vigorously to the idea that the Earth is flat?

According to those who have studied this more deeply, a fraction of those that profess belief in a 'Flat Earth' probably do so to be provocative. But let me place these people to one side, and focus on those who sincerely believe that the Earth is flat. Could they be right?

THE RISE IN THE BELIEF in a flat Earth seems to have taken hold in the mid-1800s. It appears to have developed alongside the major and rapid advances that were occurring across all of the sciences at the time.

Inevitably, perhaps, some people were uncomfortable with these advances, concerned that the natural world was being interpreted in a way that was becoming ever more deeply disconnected with the sorts of phenomena that could be experienced, explained, and understood by any one individual. Should one really accept explanations that could not, immediately and categorically, be confirmed by a rational mind?

Into this space stepped Samuel Rowbotham. In what was a primitive experiment even then, he found no noticeable curvature on a 10-km long straight drainage ditch of the Bedford Levels in East Anglia. He became convinced of the flatness of the Earth, started to lecture about it, and published a book on the subject in 1865.

The movement was continued by others, amongst them Samuel Shenton, and it remained active into the early part of the 20th century, when it went into decline. But it was revived in 1956 as [The Flat Earth Society](#).

ONE DIFFICULTY in grasping a clear picture of 'the' flat-Earth hypothesis is that different proponents often hold somewhat different viewpoints. But as I understand it, the central tenets are that the North Pole is at the centre of the flat Earth's disk, and its circumference is marked by an ice wall which is guarded (some say by NASA) to prevent anyone going beyond.

In this model, gravity is due to the flat Earth accelerating upwards, continuously, at 9.8 m s^{-2} . The Sun is a 'small' object not far above the Earth's surface (as are the Moon, planets and stars), and its motion gives rise to the seasons. I am not clear what stars are in this model, or how anything of our Galaxy's structure is interpreted.

But if we accept that the Earth is flat, are the Sun and Moon and other planets also flat? This question was put to the then president of the Flat Earth Society, Daniel Shenton, in a [Guardian podcast](#) with David Adam and Brian Cox in 2010. *'I'm not sure about them*, he said. *'It seems to me from the evidence that I've seen that they're probably spheres, but it's definitely not proven.'*

His view on space was that *'As far as the evidence of the space age, anything like that can be easily faked.'*

YOUNGOV is an internet market research and data analytics firm. In 2019, they polled views on which [science-based conspiracy theories](#) the British believe in.

You can see, from this link, the significant fraction of people who consider that the threat of climate change is over-exaggerated; that vaccines have harmful effects which are not being fully disclosed to the public; that the moon landing was staged; and that the Earth is flat.

Results of a similar [poll in the US in 2018](#), found that only 84% said with certainty that the Earth is a globe, a fraction even lower among young people at a mere 64%.

THERE IS AN important message for educators and scientists, and one which has been eloquently expounded by science communicator [Sabine Hossenfelder](#). The belief in a flat Earth has, perhaps, less to do with the shape of the Earth, and more to do with the way today's big science is conducted and communicated. The relevant institutions are too large and complex for any individual to easily comprehend.

A consequence can be that without a tolerable understanding of 'the scientific method', by which conjectures *can* be refuted, but only with solid evidence, it is not unreasonable that some will choose to mistrust anything that cannot be easily verified. While this may not matter too much in the question of whether the Earth is round or flat, the consequences will be more serious in the case of, say, uninformed views on vaccines (such as MMR and Covid), or on climate change.

In the same [Guardian podcast](#), Robert Winston argued that in hoping to tackle climate change, wider society must be 'on side', implying that scientists somehow need to communicate even better with society. And in the spirit of the flat-Earth proponents, he even emphasised the point that we should not *necessarily* trust Governments, for they may well have other (in particular, short-term) agendas, predicated on their own survival.

Brian Cox concluded that: *'Science is all about checking, but at the same time one has to accept the settled view of experts... As an idea, to be a sceptic, I like the idea of a Flat Earth Society... It's just that, in this case, they've picked the wrong thing to be sceptical about.'*

WHAT HAS ALL THIS to do with Gaia? Simply that this advanced space mission continues to add enormous weight to our global understanding of Nature, underpinned by the Earth's rotation, a massive Sun some 160 million km from Earth, and stars at vast distances.

As just one example, we can now predict, months in advance, and to within a minute or so, hundreds of star occultations by minor solar system bodies (essay #24).

Advocates of a flat Earth might enjoy the challenge of trying to predict *just one* such stellar occultation, say, a few months in advance and with a timing accuracy of better than a minute. Do we have any takers?